

Changes in net photosynthetic rate (Pn) in flag leaves of reciprocal-cross F₁ and their parents under transient low light impact.

Combination number	(Pn 500-Pn 110)/Pn 500			
	Parent 1	Parent 2	F ₁	
			Parent 1/Parent 2	Parent 2/Parent 1
1	LH422 (I) ^a	Pal (I)	0.747 ± 0.1741	0.326 ± 0.0874
	0.716 ± 0.1446	0.518 ± 0.0339		
2	YS8072 (J) ^b	Xiushui 04 (J)	0.776 ± 0.1237	0.396 ± 0.1266
	0.625 ± 0.0304	0.435 ± 0.0641		
3	Sunong 30367 (I)	02428 (J)	0.891 ± 0.0707	0.430Li ± 0.0848
	0.834 ± 0.0767	0.482 ± 0.0283		
4	LH422 (I)	Minghui 75 (I)	0.702 ± 0.1524	0.396 ± 0.0820
	0.716 ± 0.1446	0.356 ± 0.0601		
5	Luweidao (I)	Zhongguo 91 (J)	0.621 ± 0.0099	0.473 ± 0.0233
	0.702 ± 0.0693	0.361 ± 0.1277		
6	LH422 (I)	029 (J)	0.693 ± 0.0127	0.527 ± 0.0636
	0.716 ± 0.1446	0.448 ± 0.1916		
7	YS8072 (J)	Luweidao (I)	0.793 ± 0.1392	1.09 ± 0.153
	0.625 ± 0.0304	0.702 ± 0.0693		
8	02428 (J)	IET9702 (I)	0.477 ± 0.1209	0.446 ± 0.1044
	0.482 ± 0.0283	0.439 ± 0.0523		

^aI = indica subspecies. ^bJ = japonica subspecies.

small reduction in Pn, such as combination 8; 2) Pn reduction in both parents is large (such as combination 7); and 3) one parent has a large reduction in Pn and the other has a small reduction (combination 1). In the third kind of combination, performances of Pn reduction in the reciprocal cross F₁ are basically identical to those in corresponding maternal lines under low irradiation impact. Results in the other combinations also support this.

It can therefore be concluded that genes related to tolerance for transient low light stress in rice are mainly located in the cytoplasm. However, in some situations nuclear genes from both maternal and paternal lines interact with cytoplasmic genes from the maternal line to make tolerance stronger (in combination 1) or weaker (in combination 7). The large and positive correlations between Pn and accumulation of dry matter will make this genetic behavior of shared tolerance in rice useful in breeding for high yield. ■

Stress tolerance—other structures

Screening somaclonal variants with tolerance for both shade and photooxidation in rice

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Rice plants must have increased adaptation to light stresses, including shade and photooxidation, before higher photosynthesis and yield can be achieved. Somaclonal variation is a new source of tolerance for shade and photooxidation. We have obtained some somaclonal variants with tolerance for both shade and photooxidation (double tolerance) in rice.

Calli were induced on solid N6 medium with 2 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ liter from mature

caryopses of three varieties, 02428, Zhongguo 91, and 842 to both shade and photooxidation, and then subcultured on the same medium. Calli were transferred on to solid MS medium with 2 mg BA L⁻¹ + 0.25 mg NAAL⁻¹ + 0.25 mg IAA L⁻¹ to regenerate plants (R₁). Posterities of R₁ were sexually reproduced.

Somaclonal variants from different parents were identified under shade and photooxidative conditions. Rice plants were grown from booting to grain tilling (3 wk) under two layers of light gray plastic nets, which allowed about 30% natural sunlight to penetrate. Under shade, specific leaf weight declined, with less than 20% of the varieties being classified as tolerant. The upper 2d leaves were gathered at booting stage and submerged in tap water containing low CO₂ and low O₂. They were

Differential responses of rice somaclonal variants under shading and photooxidative conditions.

Somaclonal variant	Grade of photooxidation ^a	Decline of SLW (%) ^b
02428 (parent)	I	4.2
02428hong (R ₅)	II	13.4
02428h (R ₅)	I	5.3
Zhongguo 91 (parent)	I	21.3
CX-1 (R ₄)	I	14.7
842 (parent)	V	25.9
842241-1 (R ₂)	IV	19.2
842241-2 (R ₂)	III	- ^c
842houshi (R ₂)	II	31.7
84202-chou 1 (R ₂)	IV	-
84202-chou 7 (R ₂)	II	-
84202-chou 9 (R ₂)	IV	24.9
84202-chou 10 (R ₂)	II	18.6

^aI = whole leaf area green, II = only leaf tip yellow, III = 1/3 of leaf area yellow, IV = 1/2 of leaf area yellow, V = 3/4 of leaf area or whole leaf area yellow. Upper 2nd leaves from the main stems were used, replicated three times. ^bSLW = specific leaf weight. The uppermost leaves from the main stems were used, except CX-1. ^c- = not determined.

then incubated under $1400\mu\text{Em}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ at 35°C for 6 d. Treated leaves were divided into five grades based on the degree of green lost, with grades I and II being considered tolerant (see table).

Somaclonal variants have great differences in their responses to shading and photooxidative stresses (see table). Somaclonal variants with double tolerance

were obtained for both shade- and photooxidation-tolerant parent 02428 (such as 02428h and 02428hong), from photooxidation-tolerant but shade-sensitive parent Zhongguo 91 (such as CX-1), and from sensitive parent 842 to both shade and photooxidation-tolerant (such as 84202-chou 10).

The variants with double sensitivity may be particularly useful for improving culti-

vars with good agronomic characters but sensitivity to light stresses. Frequency of variants with double sensitivity or with either tolerance for shade or photooxidation from double-sensitive parents is higher, however, than that for variants with double tolerance. ■

Biochemical identification and genetic analysis of molybdenum cofactor mutants in rice

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The molybdenum cofactor (MoCo) prosthetic group is essential for the activity of molybdo enzymes, such as nitrate reductase (NR), xanthine dehydrogenase (XDH), and

sulfite oxidase. However, very little information is available on the MoCo biosynthetic pathway in rice. We report the biochemical identification and genetic analysis of MoCo-deficient mutants in rice to provide genetic information on this pathway.

Four MoCo-deficient mutants (*cnx* mutants), C25, C27, C32, and C33, were isolated as chlorate-resistant mutants from 100,000 M_2 seedlings. Biochemical analysis showed that NADH-, NADPH-NR, XDH activities, and MoCo biosynthesis abilities (MoCo activities) were deficient in these four mutants, indicating they were MoCo-deficient types (Table 1).

The *cnx* mutants could be divided into two groups: one that could recover NR activity by adding molybdate in growth medium and one that could not. To classify our *cnx* mutants, their 7-d-old seedlings were treated with Kimura's B solution containing 0.5 mM Na_2MoO_4 for 2 d. Molybdate treatment did not recover NADH-NR activity in C25 but did so in C27, C32, and C33; the activity was double that of the control (Table 1). We also investigated the tungstate sensitivity in the mutants because it has been reported that a tungstate-sensitive group exists among *Arabidopsis thaliana* *cnx* mutants. We hydroponically cultured the mutants and their wild type IR30 with culture medium containing 0.1, 1, or 10 mM Na_2MoO_4 for 7 d. In all treatments, no significant differences occurred between the mutants and IR30 in seedling height and root length. We therefore conclude that the four *cnx* mutants do not belong to the tungstate-sensitive group (Table 1).

Derived from the four cross combinations between *cnx* mutants and wild type IR30, the chlorate resistance in F_2 populations had a segregation of 3:1 wild type: mutant phenotype, indicating a single recessive gene controls each mutation (Table 2).

The allelism test, using the three F_2 populations derived from the crosses between the four *cnx* mutants, indicated that the three mutant genes of C27, C32, and C33 are located at the same locus, and that the genes of C25 and these three mutants are located at different loci (Table 2). This result coincides with the phenotypic classification based on the restoration of NADH-NR activity by molybdate as mentioned above. Thus, we conclude that at least two loci are involved in the MoCo biosynthetic pathway in rice. ■

Table 1. Characteristics of the four *cnx* mutants and wild type IR30.

Line	NADH-NR activity ^a		NADPH-NR activity ^a	MoCo activity ^b	XDH	Chlorate resistant	Tungstate sensitive
	Control	+0.5 mM Na_2MoO_4					
IR30	870.2	432.4 (49) ^c	11.3	3.8	+ ^d	S ^e	R ^e
C25	0.0	0.0 (0)	0.0	0.0	-	R	R
C27	170.0	465.4 (273)	0.3	1.4	δ	R	R
C32	207.6	467.7 (225)	1.1	1.6	δ	R	R
C33	194.6	517.8 (266)	0.0	0.4	δ	R	R

^an mol $\text{NO}_2^- \text{min}^{-1} \text{g fresh weight}^{-1}$, ^bn mol $\text{NO}_2^- \text{min}^{-1} \text{mg protein}^{-1}$. ^cPercentage of control, ^{c+} = XDH activity; δ = very low XDH activity; - = no XDH activity. ^eS = sensitive, R = resistant.

Table 2. Segregation of chlorate resistance in F_2 populations between *cnx* mutants and wild type IR30 or between *cnx* mutants.

Cross combination	Segregation in F_2 plants ^a			χ^2 value		Probability
	Chlorate-sensitive	Chlorate-resistant	Total plants (no.)	3:1	9:7	
C25/IR30	83	37	120	2.117		0.1 < P < 0.2
C27/IR30	82	34	116	1.149		0.2 < P < 0.3
C32/IR30	83	30	113	0.144		0.5 < P < 0.7
C33/IR30	90	19	109	3.330		0.05 < P < 0.1
C25/C27	102	85	187		0.220	0.5 < P < 0.7
C27/C32	0	198	198	No segregation		
C33/C27	0	168	168	No segregation		

^aThe F_2 seeds were sown in 0.1 mM KC10_3 solution at 30°C . Fourteen days after sowing, chlorate resistance was evaluated visually from the reduction in seedling height and the extent of brown spots on the leaves.